

USE OF JAPANESE EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION

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Annotation: The system for assessing the educational achievements of pupils is a way to obtain information about the quality of mastering the educational program. Assessment is a process of correlating real results with set goals, which diagnoses the pupils, reports information to the teacher in order to adjust teaching methods. However, the assessment system connects not only the student and teacher, but also other participants in the educational process: school, parents, local authorities. The connection between the participants and their influence on the educational process makes the assessment system an important and significant component of the quality of education.

Key words: PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment), TIMMS (Trends in Mathematics and Science Study), GPA (Grade Point Average), talent, education, education system, preschool, elementary, junior, high school.

In Japanese education, there is no concept of a "gifted student". because everything The student has a special talent. Among the advanced countries, Japanese education has a unique direction. happening. In particular, the structure of the Japanese education system is as follows: preschool education, elementary school, junior high school, high school, institutions of higher education that are part of higher education systems.

In elementary school teachers criticize children for their behavior teach them to criticize the bad sides, shortcomings of the school. From this it is clear that the teacher is not limited to teaching, but to each child affects the development Japan's teacher salaries are among the highest in the world. it is the only state that is even higher among. Mandatory learning environment. This level of education is from 6 to 15 years children. Financial assistance to children from low-income families is displayed. The secondary school includes grades 10-11-12, such schools There are day, part-time and evening departments. There are 80 students in the high school during the entire academic year. pass the test. Students are free to choose their core subjects in English, technical education and special tests. To universities, high school or 12-year regular school graduates will be accepted. Admission to universities is carried out in 2 stages. Stage 1 is held in a hostel for which Japanese, mathematics, tests in physics, chemistry, sociology and history. In Japan, higher education is compulsory and integrated with vocational education. depends on. In Japan, the role and responsibility of mothers in the upbringing of children is especially great.

They are a family dynasty so that their children grow up smart, intelligent and hardworking and consider themselves responsible to the state. About family education in Japan many guides and recommendations published, radio and television gives a lot of teaching advice. Home tables in Japanese families deserve attention. He's perfect, side a device protected by a bookshelf, a lamp, a clock, pencils, paper, calculator and other essentials are also needed down to panic buttons that call parents in case of an emergency

Schoolchildren from Japan ranked sixth in math literacy and fifth in science literacy - PISA. Third and second place in science 4th and 8th grade, fifth place in mathematics 4th and 8th grade - TIMSS. The high level of education quality in Japan makes it relevant to comprehend the experience of the national assessment system. School education in Japan consists of three levels: elementary school lasts six years, middle and high school three years each. After each stage, the student

must choose between public, private and special schools. Education from the first to the ninth grade is compulsory and it is free, high school is paid and completed by those who want to go to university. In elementary school, children study Japanese, mathematics, science, and physical education. Children also spend an hour on calligraphy and reading. Particular attention is paid to the education of morality and ethics through a separate subject "Moral" in which children talk about the correctness and incorrectness of certain actions. Some schools have home economics classes where children are taught basic sewing and cooking skills. Grade 1 does not use a point or letter grading system to assess student performance. At the first stage of training, teachers use the Hanamaru flower drawing to assess personal results, other types of marks are not used. The teacher draws the Hanamaru flower after the first grade as a way to increase learning motivation. The size of the petals and flower depends on the efforts that the teacher appreciated. After the first grade, the assessment and mark become confidential - all comments, marks and report cards are received by students in closed envelopes. The teacher cannot scold and discuss student progress in public. Of course, cohesion within the team allows children to independently identify the progress of each student, but directly no one except parents knows the progress of the student. Starting from the second grade, students take internal exams, which are evaluated on a 100-point system and record the results of students. At the end of primary education, textbooks take a state exam that allows them to move on to secondary school, which is also assessed on a 100-point system. Private schools may use the GPA (Grade Point Average).

The evaluation system in Japan is as follows:

For public high school students, there is a combined letter and point/percentage grading system.

- yuu(優): A (90–100) – Excellent
- Yū (優): A (80–89.99) – Very good
- ryou(良): B (70-<79) – Good

- ka(可): C (60-<69) - You have to try
- fuka(不可): F (0-<59) – Failed

The evaluation system in Uzbekistan is as follows:

- 5- Excellent
- 4- Good
- 3-Satisfactory
- 2-Unsatisfactory (collapsed)
- 1-Bad(failed)

Conclusion: Comprehensive reforms and reconstruction of education in our country experienced and continues to experience such a complex process as implementation. The goal is to democratize school activities, their humanity. Development of principles on the basis of which the content of educational work, its form and a comprehensive update and further refinement of the method. Updated education is a whole new way of thinking. At this time in executors of education of equal value, prestige and prestige of education there must also be initiative, dedication and enterprise. Success in education is on the side of the most courageous people. Bold actions are conditioned by courage. At the same time, of course, we must use the education system of experienced countries. Above, we studied the education system of Japan, one of the developed countries. In Uzbekistan, we can achieve effective results if we use similar methods. From the above, it can be seen that the education system in Japan is both formal and informal has a high degree of coherence. Worth to learn a lot. Forexample: Thorough preparation of the child for school. Strengthen parental responsibility for the education and upbringing of children. Attention is paid to the physical development of students. High demand for teaching staff. Consistent work with young talents. If we can apply such a system, we will definitely achieve the desired result.

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